

Benzo- or naphthoquinolino[6,7-d]furan-6,11-dione (3-6): A mixture of 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-dione (0.005 mol) and phenol (0.005 mol) was refluxed in pyridine for 8–10 h until the reaction mixture had a permanent colour and yielded a dark solid. The reaction mixture was then cooled and resulting solid was washed with boiling water and crystallised from acetic acid (Table 1).

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Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Synthesis and Anti-microbial Activity of 1,4-Bis(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-ylamino)phthalazine

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4-THIAZOLIDINONES¹ and phthalazines² possess various biological activities. Dihydralazine is a potent antihypertensive agent³. With a view to obtaining better therapeutic agents we have synthesised different 4-thiazolidinones (3) by the action of thioglycolic acid on Schiff bases obtained by condensing 1,4-dihydrazinophthalazine with different aryl aldehydes (Scheme 1). The structures were supported by ir, mass and pmr spectral studies. The products were screened for anti-microbial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on Varian-400 spectrometer.

1,4-Bis(substituted-benzaldehydrazino)phthalazine: A mixture of 1,4-dihydrazinophthalazine (1.9 g,

0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (3.32 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in methanol was refluxed for 15 min on a water-bath. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bisulphite, dried and crystallised from methanol, (54%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 68.70, N, 17.04. $C_{26}H_{26}N_6O_4$ requires: C, 68.83, N, 17.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) ($R=3,4$ -dimethoxy phenyl) 3 300 (NH), 1 660 (C=N) and 810 cm^{-1} (ring skeletal); δ ($CDCl_3$) ($R=3,4$ -dimethoxy phenyl) 8.6 (2H, s, CH=N), 7.53 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 7.23 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 7.25

Scheme 1

(2H, s, CH aromatic), 6.90 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 6.93 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 3.98 (6H, s, OCH₃), 3.90 (6H, s, OCH₃) and 10.95 (2H, s, NH); *m/z* (R=3,4-dimethoxyphenyl) 323, 162, 160, 137, 131, 116, 107, 101, 93 and 89.

Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

1,4 Bis(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-ylamino) phthalazine (3): A mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) and 1,4-bis(substituted benzalhydrazino)-phthalazine (0.01 mole) was refluxed for 10 h on an oil-bath at 110°–20°. It was then cooled and washed with sodium bicarbonate. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol-dioxane (1 : 1), (52%), *m p* 130° (Found : C, 56.70; N, 13.19; S, 9.94. C₃₀H₃₀N₆O₆S₂ requires : C, 56.78; N, 13.25; S, 10.09); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) (R=3,4-dimethoxyphenyl) 3 250 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 685 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); *m/z* 307, 258, 204, 161, 129, 102, 101, 89, 75, 47 and 44.

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	Schiff bases	4-Thiazolidinones
		M.p. °C	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	150	low m.p.
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	145	low m.p.
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	182	140(d)
4.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	211	190
5.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	180	180
6.	3-Aminophenyl	300	145(d)
7.	4-Aminophenyl	225(d)	310(d)
8.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	137	205
9.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	208	260(d)
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	112	110
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	160	115(d)
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	184	130
13.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-phenyl	115(d)	220
14.	3-Nitrophenyl	175	110(d)
15.	Cinnamyl	140	240(d)
16.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	160	90

Antimicrobial activity: 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate⁴ method. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 µg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluores* and fungi *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Most of the compounds showed moderate activity (zone of inhibition=14–22 mm) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(3'-Chloro-4'-aryl-2'-azetidion-1'-yl)-4-(2"-methyl-4"-hydroxy-5"-isopropylphenyl)thiazoles

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IN view of the powerful antibiotic activity shown by β -lactams¹ and wide-range therapeutic activity shown by thiazole derivatives², we have undertaken the synthesis of 2-azetidiones bearing thiazole moiety of the type 2 by the action of chloro acetyl chloride on Schiff bases (1) in the presence of basic catalyst. The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

4-Acetocthymol³ is obtained by condensing thymol to Frie's migration reaction in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using nitrobenzene as solvent, which on condensation with thiourea in presence of iodine gives 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole⁴. This on further reaction with different aromatic aldehydes in presence of methanol yields Schiff bases (1a-t).